

DIPLOMATIC RELATIONS OF NADR MUHAMMADKHAN IN THE BUKHARA KHANATE**Beknazarov Javoxir Azimjon o'g'li**

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Annotation: This article was used historical and content analysis, comparison, and systematization methods in its writing. It explores the foreign policy and diplomatic activities of Nadr Muhammad Khan, the ruler of the Bukhara Khanate in the 17th century. Drawing on historical sources, the article analyzes his diplomatic missions to Safavid Iran, the Mughal Empire in India, Russia, the Ottoman Empire, and neighboring khanates. The article highlights how the ruler used diplomacy (through envoys, gifts, and alliances) to protect Bukhara's political interests, reclaim disputed territories like Balkh, and strengthen trade and geopolitical ties. The article also focuses on Nadr Muhammad Khan's relations with Ottoman Sultan Mehmed IV, Safavid Shahs Abbas I and II, Mughal Emperor Shah Jahan, and Russian Tsar Mikhail Fyodorovich. Information about the diplomatic missions of ambassadors: Poyanda Mirzo, Vaqqos Khoja, Qozikhon, Tarbiyatkhon, Kozi Noghay, Saloy Bahodir, as well as information about palace positions responsible for diplomacy in the Bukhara khanate: *Nakib, Udaychi, Shighavul, Arbab*, is also provided.

Keywords: Political history, Bukhara Khanate, Nadr Muhammad Khan, Ottoman Empire, Mughal Empire, Safavid Iran, Russia, Balkh in 17th century, Embassy, Foreign relations.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada tarixiy va content tahlil, taqqoslash va tizimlashtirish metodlari qo'llanilgan. Maqola XVII-asrda Buxoro xoni hukmdori Nadr Muhammadxonning tashqi siyosati va diplomatik faoliyatini tadqiq etadi. Tarixiy manbalarga tayanib, maqolada uning Safaviylar Eroniga, Hindistondagi Boburiylar imperiyasiga, Rossiyaga, Usmonli imperiyasiga va qo'shni xonliklarga yuborgan diplomatik missiyalari tahlil qilinadi. Maqola hukmdorning diplomatiyasi (elchilar, sovg'alar va ittifoqlar orqali) qanday qilib Buxoroning siyosiy manfaatlarini himoya qilishi, Balx kabi bahsli hududlarni qayta egallashi, savdo va geosiyosiy aloqalarni mustahkamlashda qanday yo'llardan foydalanganligini yoritadi. Shuningdek, biz Nadr Muhammad Xonning Usmonli Sultoni Mehmed IV, Safaviy Shoh Abbas I va II, Hind imperatori Shoh Jahon va Rossiya hukmdori podsho Mixail Fyodorovich bilan bo'lgan aloqalariga ham e'tibor qaratamiz. Elchilar: Poyanda Mirzo, Vaqqosxo'ja, Qozixon, Tarbiyatxon, Qozi No'g'ay, Saloy Bahodirning elchiliklari to'g'risidagi ma'lumotlari, shuningdek, Buxoro xonligidagi elchilik uchun mas'ul bo'lgan saroydagi lavozimlar: *Naqib, Udaychi, Shig'ovul, Arbob* haqida ma'lumot beramiz.

Kalit so'zlar: Siyosiy tarix, Buxoro Xonligi, Nadr Muhammad Xon, Usmonli imperiyasi, Boburiylar imperiyasi, Safaviylar Eroni, Rossiya, XVII-asrda Balx, Elchilik, Tashqi aloqalar.

Аннотация: В статье использованы методы исторического и контентного анализа, сравнения и систематизации. Рассматривается внешняя политика и дипломатическая деятельность Надира Мухаммеда Хана, правителя Бухарского ханства в XVII веке.

Основываясь на исторических источниках, статья анализирует его дипломатические миссии в Сефевидский Иран, Могольскую империю в Индии, Россию, Османскую империю и соседние ханства. Освещается, как правитель использовал дипломатию (через посланников, подарки и союзы) для защиты политических интересов Бухары, возвращения спорных территорий, таких как Балх, и укрепления торговых и геополитических связей. Также внимание уделяется отношениям Надара Мухаммеда Хана с Османским султаном Мехмедом IV, Сефевидскими шахами Аббасом I и II, индийским императором Шахом Джаханом и русским царем Михаилом Федоровичем. Приводятся данные о дипломатических миссиях послов: Поянды Мирзы, Ваккоса Ходжи, Кози хана, Тарбийатхана, Кози Ногая, Салеи Баходира, а также информация о придворных должностях, ответственных за дипломатию в Бухарском ханстве: *Накиб, Удайчи, Шихавул, Арбаб.*

Ключевые слова: Политическая история, Бухарское ханство, Надар Мухаммед Хан, Османская империя, Могольская империя, Сефевидский Иран, Россия, Балх в XVII веке, Посольства, Внешние отношения.

Özet: Bu makale, tarihi ve içerik analiz, karşılaştırma ve sistematizasyon yöntemlerini kullanarak yazılmıştır. Makale, 17. yüzyılda Buhara Hanlığı hükümdarı Nadr Muhammed Han'ın dış politikası ve diplomatik faaliyetlerini incelemektedir. Tarihsel kaynaklara dayanarak, makalede onun Safevi İrani, Hindistan'daki Babür İmparatorluğu, Rusya, Osmanlı İmparatorluğu ve komşu hanlıklarla yaptığı diplomatik misyonlar analiz edilmektedir. Makale, hükümdarın diplomasi yöntemlerini (elçiler, hediyeler ve ittifaklar aracılığıyla) Buhara'nın siyasi çıkarlarını korumak, Belh gibi tartışmalı toprakları yeniden ele geçirmek ve ticaret ile jeopolitik bağları güçlendirmek için nasıl kullandığını vurgulamaktadır. Ayrıca, Nadr Muhammed Han'ın Osmanlı Sultanı IV. Mehmed, Safevi Şahları I. ve II. Abbas, Babür İmparatoru Şah Cihan ve Rus Çarı Mihail Fyodoroviç ile olan ilişkilerine de odaklanılmaktadır. Elçiler: Poyanda Mirzo, Vaqqos Hoca, Qozihan, Tarbiyathan, Kozi Noğay, Saloy Bahodir'in diplomatik görevleri ile ilgili bilgiler ve ayrıca Buhara Hanlığı'ndaki diplomasi ile sorumlu saray pozisyonları: *Nakib, Udayçi, Şihavul, Arbab* hakkında bilgi verilmektedir.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Siyasi tarih, Buhara Hanlığı, Nadr Muhammed Han,, Osmanlı İmparatorluğu, Babür İmparatorluğu, Safevi İran'ı, Rusya, 17. yüzyılda Belh, Elçilik, Dış ilişkiler.

Introduction

Due to foreign policy and diplomacy, states are consistently developing. Today, the relations between Uzbekistan, Turkey, India, Pakistan, Iran, and the countries of the Middle East are steadily growing. The roots of this development can undoubtedly be traced back to the past. Specifically, in the 17th century, cultural, economic, and military relations between these countries were well-developed. For this reason, in this article, we will take a closer look at political history. The 17th century was a developing period for the Bukhara Khanate, marked by active and strategic diplomacy under the reigns of Nadr Muhammad Khan. Ruler pursued dynamic foreign policies aimed at strengthening Bukhara's regional influence amid shifting political landscapes. Nadr Muhammad Khan forged key diplomatic ties with Safavid Iran, the Mughal Empire, and Russia, using the exchange of embassies, gifts and alliances to bolster Bukhara's prestige and security. His interactions with Shah Abbas I and Shah Jahan reflected a

nuanced approach to balancing power and diplomacy, particularly during his struggles over Balkh.

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS.

1. Foreign policy during the reign of Nadr Muhammad khan

During the reign of Nadr Muhammad Khan, unique diplomatic relations were also established with neighboring states. Taking into account his family connections with the famous Khurasani shaykhs, Nadr Muhammad exchanged envoys with Shah Abbas I. During the time of Nadr Muhammad's governorship in Balkh, he sent an envoy to Shah Abbas I. The envoy, *Chehra oghasi* Poyanda, was an able, eloquent, and intelligent diplomat who was received by Shah Abbas in Isfahan in early 1622. Rustam Muhammad, the son of Vali Muhammad, made several attempts to attack Balkh with the help of Shah Abbas. Poyanda's duty was to inform Shah Abbas I that Nadr Muhammad was dissatisfied with the attacks on Balkh by Rustam Muhammad and that he wished to establish friendly relations with Shah Abbas, provided that Rustam Muhammad be placed under control. During the conquest of Kandahar, Shah Abbas did not want the Bukhara and Balkh armies to attack Khorasan. Therefore, Shah Abbas sent Poyanda along with his envoy Muhammad Solihbek, who would deliver the friendly message to the governor of Balkh. (Audrey Burton, 2019,160) Through his envoy Poyanda Mirzo, Nadr Muhammad sent many gifts to Shah Abbas I, including 45 *hisori* and *badakhshani* horses. The envoy was warmly received by Abbas I. (İsgəndər bəy Münşi Türkman, 2014, 1712) In the following period, relations between Shah Abbas II (1642-1667) of Iran and Nadr Muhammad were strong. A key event in this was in 1645, when the deposed ruler of Balkh sought help from the Mughal Emperor Shah Jahan. (Tursun Sultanov, 2021, 185) The emperor sent his sons Aurangzeb and Murad Bakhsh to conquer Balkh. They defeated Nadr Muhammad's son, Khisrav Sultan, and captured him, sending him to India as a prisoner. Upon hearing of this, Nadr Muhammad was forced to flee through Shibirgan and Marv to Iran, where he sought refuge with Shah Abbas II. Shah Abbas II welcomed Nadr Muhammad with great respect. According to historical sources, the Shah personally went out of the city with his dignitaries and met Nadr Muhammad two hours away from the city. He gave the Bukharian Khan a noble horse as a gift and escorted him back into the city in a show of high honor. Nadr Muhammad's diplomatic ties with India began during his time as the ruler of Balkh. Notably, he established relations with Shah Jahan (the ruler of India from 1627 to 1658). In 1632, Nadr Muhammad sent his envoy Vakkos khoja to India. In response, the Indian ruler sent a mission led by Tarbiyat khan to Nadr Muhammad. (Nizamiddinov, 2012, 170) As for relations with Russia, Nadr Muhammad continued the diplomatic ties that had been established before his reign. In 1640, the Bukhara envoy Kozikhon, accompanied by 200 officials and 100 camels carrying goods, traveled to Tobolsk. This diplomatic mission was lavish, with 37 people carrying the khan's gifts. During the reign of Nadr Muhammad khan, diplomatic and trade relations with Russia were maintained. (Jukovskiy S.V, 2022, 29) In March 1643, shortly after Nadr Muhammad ascended the throne (1642–1645), he sent a letter to Tsar Mikhail Fyodorovich of Russia, expressing the intention to continue trade and the exchange of prisoners between the two countries. According to preserved records, Gribov received the Russian envoy, and in return, Noghay Yuz was sent as the Russian response envoy. (Akbar Zamonov, 2021, 61) At various times, Nadr Muhammad khan sent Saloy Bahodir, Ibrohimkhoja, Amin Bahodir, and Kozi Noghay as envoys to Moscow. Kozi Noghay spent the winter of 1643–1644 years in Astrakhan. They traveled to Moscow via the Volga river and were received with distinction upon arrival. On September 5, 1644, the Tsar sent horses to greet Kozi Noghay, and the envoys were dressed in official attire for the diplomatic ceremony. Around the

Tsar were the highest-ranking nobles, the Sheremetevs and Volkonskys, dressed in gold and black clothing. Also present were the Greek Archbishop Makarios and several elderly Greeks, which signaled interest in the envoy and his ruler. The ceremony that day closely resembled that of Odambiy's earlier visit. However, this time the Tsar did not offer his hand to be kissed; instead, he placed his hand on the envoy's head. During the ceremony, Kozi Noghay presented several gifts to the Tsar on behalf of the khan. These included:

- a cotton and silk tent, a silk belt from Kashan fabric typically worn during official ceremonies.
- and a variety of fabrics.
- such as damask, silk, muslin, velvet, and taffeta — some of which were woven with gold thread.

Additionally, he gave the Tsar personal gifts, including various striped fabrics, some also interwoven with gold thread. In his reply letter, the Tsar raised several issues: the matter of the Noghays, trade tariffs, the release of Russian slaves, and the continuation of friendly relations. He sent Nadr Muhammad khan four falcons and 33 kg of walrus ivory. (Audrey Burton, 2019, 222-233)

The next envoy, Saloy Bahodir, arrived in Moscow on January 11, 1645, carrying a letter from the Nadr Muhammad khan. Nothing specific is known about his mission, but it is possible that, since Ibrohimkhoja was still being held in Moscow, Saloy Bahodir inquired about his fate and demanded his release.

In 1648, Nadr Muhammad khan sent a letter to Istanbul with the envoy Abdumannon. The letter described internal unrest in the khanate, attacks by the Jungars, and conflicts with Abdulaziz khan. On March 30, 1649, another group of envoys was sent to Sultan Mehmed IV. They brought lavish gifts:

- a sword and dagger encrusted with precious stones.
- five valuable goblets.
- 27 cubits of gold-embroidered fabric.
- 10 horses.
- a gold-adorned saddle.
- and other precious items.

Picture of Nadr Muhammad khan 1647-1648th years.

These envoys stayed in contact with Nadr Muhammad khan for two weeks and sent letters about the diplomatic affairs in Istanbul. Mehmed IV sent letters to the Mughal ruler Shah Jahan and the Safavid ruler Shah Abbas, demanding an end to the disputes with Bukhara. He also sent a letter to Bukhara supporting the reinstatement of Nadr Muhammad khan to the throne. (Vasiliev.A, 2014, 93) In 1651, after Abdulaziz khan seized Balkh from Nadr Muhammad khan, Nadr Muhammad fled to the Simnan province of Iran, where he died later that same year. (Azamat Ziyo, 2000, 266)

2. Positions responsible for diplomatic affairs in the Bukhara khanate

We must also take a look at the diplomatic rituals of the Bukhara Khanate. In both the Bukhara Khanate and Balkh, all positions were divided into four categories and more than ten ranks based on their level of importance. According to the Russian diplomats, the Pazuhin brothers, and relying on the information from Alikseev, the reason for this classification can be found in the organization of the rituals themselves. The Pazuhins wrote: Abdulaziz khan was in his throne, and the area where the khan sat was called the "Kurinish" this area was situated at a height of six steps. No one occupied the two steps closest to the khan, and from the fourth step onward, officials were seated. On the throne itself, there were four cushions, upon which the khan sat. Among the Ashtarkhanid rulers, the left side was considered the most honorable in official ceremonies. (Alikseev A.K, 2006,140)

There are also positions responsible for diplomatic rituals and embassy affairs. *Udaychi*: In the early 18th century, the duties of the *Udaychi*'s changed slightly. The *Udaychi* became a special attendant in his own right. He was the person responsible for the ceremonies held in the Khanate and the palace, and he performed the task of escorting ambassadors or respected individuals up to the Khan or Amir. (Mir Muhammad Amin Buxoriy,1957,195)

Shighavul: The head of those who manage access to the khan's palace, an official responsible for formally bringing foreign visitors, guests, ambassadors and high-ranking officials into the presence of the khan. (Xoja Samandar Termiziy, 2001, 333)

Arbab: He was responsible for supplying the ambassadors' horses and other animals with fodder obtained from the local population. The Moscow ambassadors equated the arbob to the city governor, and he had other duties as well. (Mo'minov Ibrohim,1970, 587)

Nakib: The Naqib performed diplomatic and ambassadorial duties in the Khanate. Naqibs often served as ambassadors to foreign countries. (Semenov A.A, 1948,142)

Conclusion

The reigns of Nadr Muhammad khan represents a crucial era in the diplomatic history of the Bukhara khanate, marked by proactive engagement with neighboring powers. Their foreign policies were characterized by a calculated balance of political pragmatism and strategic alliance-building. Nadr Muhammad leveraged diplomatic ties with Iran, India, and Russia not only to secure support in times of political instability, such as during his exile from Balkh, but also to enhance Bukhara's international standing. Their missions were often accompanied by

carefully chosen gifts and symbolic gestures, reinforcing the khanate's position in regional politics.

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